

Notes on two hairy crab spiders *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The two crab spiders *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901 resemble each other and are frequently misidentified. The differences between the two species are discussed and the general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: Afrotropical Region, egg laying, maternal care, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Thomisidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Presently, 38 genera of the Thomisidae represented by 143 species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Although large numbers of specimens were collected, little is still known about specific generic and species behaviour.

The genus *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805 is represented by 143 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and 15 species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). The genus includes a group of spiders characterised by short, robust bodies, with the first two pairs of legs stout and the lateral eyes situated on distinct eye tubercles. Two of the species are recognised by their hirsute appearance have been identified from the survey samples as *T. granulatus* Karsch, 1880 and *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901.

The two species resemble each other and are frequently misidentified. In this paper we provide more information on the general morphology of both species and live photographs are provided with notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. SANSa made requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several sets of photographs of these two species were received from the public.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Both species are African endemics, with *T. granulatus* described by Karsch (1880) from Malawi and *T. spiculosus* by Pocock, 1901 from Zimbabwe. Both sexes of the two species are known and were revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

The integuments of the females differ in colour as well as the number of tubercles and setae on the body and legs. In *T. granulatus* the body is pale cream and covered by small white tubercles giving it a granulous appearance and some of the tubercles bear short to longer erect spiniform setae (Fig. 3). In *T. spiculosus* there are fewer tubercles but each bears longer and more hair-like setae (Fig. 4) giving it a hirsute appearance and the colour varies from yellow to greenish-grey.

In the males, both species are hirsute but in *T. granulatus* the male is reddish brown (Fig. 5), while in *T. spiculosus* the male resembles the female (Fig. 14).

Figure 1–4. Female: 1. *Thomisus granulatus* dorsal view. 2. *T. spiculosus* dorsal view. 3. *T. granulatus* eye pattern. 4. *T. spiculosus* eye pattern. Photo credits: 1. Bruce Blake. 2. Peter Webb. 3. Desiré Pelser. 4. Peter Webb.

***Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880**

Thomisus granulatus Karsch, 1880: 382; Lessert, 1923: 173; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 15; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 50. *Thomisus hystrix* Lawrence, 1947: 25 (name preoccupied, Nicolet, 1849).

Thomisus lawrencei Roewer, 1951: 449 (replacement name); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 15 (synonym).

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (Figs 5, 7, 10). Size: Total length 9–10 mm. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous small polyp-like tubercles, of which the tips are white; each tubercle provided with a spiniform seta (Fig. 7). Colour of body and legs creamish white, the small tubercles giving it a spotted appearance. Carapace translucent with a white broad medial band; eye area with brown triangle area (Fig. 3). Abdomen creamy white with strong abdominal tubercles (Figs 5 & 7). Epigyne circular, varies slightly in shape between individuals (Fig. 10).

Male much smaller than female (Figs 5–6). Size: TL 3 mm. Colour of carapace, abdomen reddish brown; clothed with strong setae (Fig. 6); area around eyes paler. Abdomen also with tubercles. Legs: coxae, trochanters and femora of legs I and II same colour as carapace; patellae, tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II blackish brown; tibiae with dense setae; rest of legs like carapace. Palp with retrolateral apophysis triangular in shape (Figs 8–9).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Botswana, Malawi, Namibia, Zambia, Swaziland, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Fort Grey (-33.19, 27.12); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Gate (-28.1, 32.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Kosi Bay (-28.33, 31.08); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Lake Sibhayi (-27.35, 32.7); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umzumbe (-30.61, 30.54); Makatini Flats (-27.25, 32.22); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.33, 31.08); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Umzumbe (-30.61, 30.54); Gilboa Plantation, Natal Midlands (-29.25, 30.34); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Malipsdrift (-24.22, 29.83); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Strydom Tunnel (-24.4, 30.61); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Tshulu (Venda) 2.58, 30.81); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95).

Mpumalanga: Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Hector-spruit (-25.43, 31.68); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Witrivier (-25.31, 31.02).

Western Cape: Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

Figures 5–7. *Thomisus granulatus*: 5. Female with red male on her abdomen. 6. Male anterior view. 7. Female from Lephahlale dorsal view. Photo credits: 5–6. Bruce Blake. 7. Peter Webb.

Figures 8–10. *Thomisus granulatus*: 8–9. Male palp ventral view. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 8 & 10. Line drawings after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

***Thomisus spiculosus* Pocock, 1901**

Thomisus spiculosus Pocock, 1901: 340; Comellini, 1957: 27; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 11; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 59.

Thomisus dottrensi Comellini, 1957: 10, f. 18–19 (synonym)

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (Figs 11–15). Total length 7–8 mm. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous long, spiniform setae, each seta situated on a small tubercle; some setae, as well as their bases, darker than rest. Carapace fawn with pale green to grey broad bands over carapace; eye region with reddish triangle; carapace high, slightly wider than long; both eye rows recurved, anterior row more so than posterior row. Abdomen fawn with a yellowish tint; also with strong abdominal tubercles; decorated dorsally with five pale spots. Epigynum oval with medium septum (Fig. 15). Male. TL 3–6 mm. Colour of carapace dark brown, slightly darker around edge (Fig. 12); chelicerae dark brown; abdomen yellowish brown; legs same colour as carapace except metatarsi and tarsi I and II, which are slightly paler in colour than rest of legs. Palp tibiae with short median and retro-lateral apophyses (Fig. 14).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Democratic Republic of the Congo, Nigeria, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36).

KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blydepoort (-24.74, 30.58); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Leydsdorp, Shilowani (-23.98, 30.53); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Shewasaula, Mt Sibasa (-23.5, 30.37); Luvhondo Nature reserve (-23.04, 29.44); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Mphaphuli Cycad Reserve (-22.42, 30.49); Lephallale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93).

Mpumalanga: Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

***Thomisus granulatus*:** There are no known threats to the species and in South Africa it is recorded from several protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2008) and Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001). No conservation actions are recommended.

***Thomisus spiculosus*:** There are no known threats to the species and it is protected in the following reserves: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Makalali Game Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2016) and Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

Figures 11–15. *Thomisus spiculosus*: 11. Female dorsal view. 12. Male dorsal view. 13. Female anterior view. 14. Male palp. 15. Epigyne. Photo credits: 11–13. Bruce Blake. 14–15. Line drawings of genitalia after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983)

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Figures 16–18. *Thomisus granulatus*: 16. Female on egg sac. 17–18. Female with spiderlings. Photo credits: 16–17. John Richter. 18. Desiré Pelser.

BEHAVIOUR

The two species occur sympatrically several localities. They are free-living plant dwellers sampled during beating and sweeping from vegetation. They have been sampled from all the floral biomes except the more arid biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). It was also sampled in citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Several images of the females of *T. granulatus* were received showing the female on her egg sac that she attached to the underside of a leaf (Fig. 20). The female takes up position on the egg sac where she stays until the spiderlings emerge. Several photographs were taken showing the spiderlings crawling over her body but their presence does not seem to bother her (Figs 21–22). Adults were sampled from September to December, and males during November and December. As predators they feed on a variety of insects, such as Lantana bugs (Fig. 19).

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Figures 19. *Thomisus spiculosis* female feeding on Lantana bugs. Photo credit: Desiré Pelser.

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